

Ocean and Coastal Management

Screening and assessing physical pressures affecting seafloor integrity in the Mediterranean region --Manuscript Draft--

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Abstract:	Ecosystem based management requires assessment of human activities and generated pressures that cause physical disturbance and loss of the seabed within the Mediterranean, also accounting for the strength of their interaction. To support the implementation of Descriptor 6 of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), the present work aimed at testing the applicability of an exposure-effect methodology and harmonizing - across countries sharing the same marine waters - the identification of the MSFD key physical pressures on benthic habitats and their relative importance

	<p>at different spatial scales (national, subregional, regional) in the Mediterranean Sea. The methodology uses 24 MSFD relevant human activities, 5 physical pressures, and 13 Broad Habitat Types (BHT). The links between human activities, physical pressures and the different MSFD BHT affected are identified and scored using three criteria; namely Spatial Extent, Frequency of Occurrence, and Degree of Impact. The methodology assesses the risk of pressures in a semi-quantitative way, integrating both quantitative (data) and qualitative (expert judgement) information, where quantitative data is not available, and allows the ranking of the physical pressures affecting the seafloor. The methodology was applied in the marine waters of Italy, Slovenia, Croatia and Greece. Abrasion (e.g., related to fishing or boating) and sealing (e.g., caused by structures) were ranked as top pressures; the former is widespread over different BHTs, in a persistent manner and presents intense impacts; the latter appears locally, at specific sites, persistently, generating an acute impact. According to the results, the infralittoral and circalittoral habitats are those most affected by physical pressures. The identification of major pressures can assist considerably towards the elimination or mitigation of the impacts through actions on the human activities, as it enables the prioritisation of tailor-made measures to achieve or maintain the Good Environmental Status (GES) in the region.</p>
<p>Suggested Reviewers:</p>	<p>Arantza Murillas amurillas@azti.es</p> <p>Louisa Giannoudi giannoudi@hcmr.gr</p> <p>Panos Panagiotidis ppanag@ath.hcmr.gr</p> <p>Laurent Guerin laurent.guerin@mnhn.fr</p>
<p>Response to Reviewers:</p>	<p>Theodora Paramana Laboratory of Environmental Chemistry, Faculty of Chemistry, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Athens, Greece. Email: tparaman@geol.uoa.gr Tel: +30 6977296226/ +30 210 727 4724</p> <p>January 15th, 2024</p> <p>Dear Reviewers, On behalf of my co-authors and me, please find enclosed our revised manuscript entitled 'Screening and assessing physical pressures affecting seafloor integrity in the Mediterranean region' submitted for consideration to Ocean & Coastal Management bearing the Manuscript Number OCMA-D-23-00541. The authors contributed to the revision of the manuscript supporting that achieving a proper management of the marine environment, following the Ecosystem-based approach, requires accurate and thorough assessments of its environmental status, of the human activities and generated pressures that cause physical disturbance and loss of the seabed, while accounting for the strength of their interaction. The manuscript has been revised in accordance with your comments and suggestions. We are really grateful for the time and effort you dedicated to the present work, as we believe that trying to address your comments, we have introduced amendments that have considerably improved the quality of the manuscript. Please find below all the changes that have been made to the manuscript. My co-authors and I would like to thank you in advance for considering these alterations.</p> <p>Yours faithfully,</p> <p>Theodora Paramana</p> <p>Responses to Reviewers</p> <p>Reviewer #1</p>

1. Methodology

- Lines 47-50, page 3, I would recommend to include information about why authors use 3 impact risk criteria instead of 5 to let the readers know the reasoning behind their choice.

Response: Thank you for this suggestion, we added text in the methodology explaining why (lines 158-161) and in the conclusions section supporting how this could be done in a second step after revision (lines 678-683).

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Response: The evidence sources are provided in the manuscript below Table 3 (lines 240-243).

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Response: Thank you for this comment. Please consider that TR is total risk. The methodology section mentioned was reworded and the definition of Total Risk was clarified (lines 201-206). To avoid confusion the terms used are Impact Risk (IR) and Total Risk (%TR) throughout the document. Furthermore, the description of the SPSS options (explore) used for analysis was also improved (lines 219-221).

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Response: The citation was added next to the formula as requested.

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Response: The recommendation was adopted throughout the text.

2. Results

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Response: Thank you for this comment. Although we find reason in the suggestion, we have retained the order to reflect the methodology. Risk assessment is STEP C that precedes pressure ranking that is STEP D, which in fact is possible after assigning a score to the criteria. Additionally, as suggested, the text and figures presented in the results section were reduced. The original sections 3.2.2-3.2.4 have been moved to supplementary material. Therefore, pressure ranking, which constitutes the main objective of the paper, appears earlier in the text in the revised version of the manuscript and thus it is more noticeable.,

- Methods information in results section: Section 3.1. First paragraph of results (lines 7-

10, page 6) is part of methods for me. To present an introduction and repeat the research question is helpful in the results section as it smooth flow of information, but it should not repeat the methods. I would suggest to rephrase Section 3.1. first paragraph of results (lines 7-10, page 6) so that it does not focus on methods or move it to methods. The same happens with lines 9-14, page 7, here, it is referring to methods. I would suggest moving from results those lines with methodological information to methods section.

Response: Thank you for this comment. The first paragraph of section 3.1 was rephrased to facilitate the flow of the text. Lines 7-10 on page 6, and lines 9-14 on page 7 mentioning methodology were removed.

- I would recommend to change the name of section 3.4 to "descriptive statistics".

Response: The section title was changed according to the recommendation.

- It would be helpful to reduce the use of acronyms particularly in results, as it would make easier the flow of information and understanding.

Response: The use of acronyms was reduced to the extent possible. However, the acronyms relating to the assessment areas of Italy, i.e., MAD, MIC and MWE, were retained for space purposes.

- The figure 1 is very interesting as it is showing which activities are associated with which type of pressure per country. Thus, I would recommend to extend a bit more the text of section 3.1. Further, I would recommend to clarify this sentence "to these activities present slight differences, possibly showing an inconsistency in the relative role (e.g., negligible vs not negligible) of the pressures associated to each activity." What does it mean with inconsistency in the relative role?

Response: Thank you for this comment. The text regarding Figure 1 was extended. The sentence indicated has been rephrased for clarity (lines 248-251).

3. Discussion

- As the guide for authors of the journal indicates, the discussion should explore the significance of the results of the work, not repeat them. Following this guidance, I would recommend to reduce the amount of results that is included in the discussion. For example, see page 17 lines 4-48, here results are being repeated, which should be in results instead of discussion. I would recommend to have a first short paragraph with the main results instead and put the results information in the results section.

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- After that first brief paragraph of main results, I would recommend to elaborate more on the discussion of results of the analysis, so adding for example a paragraph comparing them to similar assessments performed in the Mediterranean Sea (including relevant references).

Response: Thank you for the comment. Examples and references were added in the text. The discussion section has been modified throughout following the comments and recommendations, therefore modifications are not indicated in specific lines as they are numerous.

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Response: The use of site footprint refers to the smallest footprint considered by the method as shown in Table 2. The sentence was rewritten for clarity.

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- There are references between brackets that do not appear in the reference list. I would recommend to include them in the reference list so readers know what these references mean. Examples: see line 39, page 19, "(com dec 848 reference)" and line 46, "(D6C5 criterion)".

Response: The reference list has been amended accordingly.

- As of the reference list, in the author guidelines appear "List: References should be arranged first alphabetically and then further sorted chronologically if necessary". The reference list is not currently following the guidelines. The guide for authors can be found in Ocean and Coastal Management website.

Response: The reference list has been amended to conform to the journal guidelines.

5. General comments

- There are several cases in which capital first letters are used instead of minor letter. E.g. Abrasion, Sealing, Other physical disturbance, Other physical loss, Hydrological changes, Scoring Table, and so on. I would suggest to change to minor letters.

Response: The changes have been made from capital letters to minor letters throughout the text for Abrasion, Sealing, Other physical disturbance, Other physical loss, Hydrological changes, Scoring Table. However, activities and Broad Habitat Types words start with capital letter so they are noticeable in the text and avoid confusion.

- I would recommend to be consistent with the use of decimal point, in some cases a comma is used for the decimal (see figure 10).

Response: Necessary corrections have been made throughout the document.

- I would recommend not having a space between the % symbol and the number. E.g. 12%. Throughout the text, in some places there is a space and in others not. Consistency is needed.

Response: All such cases have been corrected throughout the manuscript.

- I would use "MS" instead of "MSs" as it is the most used acronym for member states.

Response: Thank you for the suggestion. MS has been used throughout the document.

- It would be helpful to reduce the use of acronyms. If possible, it would be helpful also to include a list of acronyms.

Response: A list of acronyms has been included. Acronyms have been retained when referring to MS for reasons of space and when using directive terminology such as GES, MSFD.

List of acronyms

BHT: Broad Habitat Types

D6: Descriptor 6

DI: Degree of Impact

EO: Ecosystem Overviews

FO: Frequency of Occurrence

GES: Good Environmental Status

GR: Greece

HELCOM: Convention on the Protection of the Marine Environment of the Baltic Sea Area

HR: Croatia

ICES: International Council for the Exploration of the Sea.

IT: Italy

MAD: Adriatic Sea

MAL: Aegean-Levantine Sea

MIC: Ionian Sea and Central Mediterranean Sea

MS: Member State(s)

MSCG: Commission Expert Group on Strategic Coordination for the MSFD

MSFD: Marine Strategy Framework Directive

MWE: Western Mediterranean Sea

SE: Spatial Extent

SL: Slovenia

TG Seabed: EU Technical group on seabed habitats and sea-floor integrity

- I would recommend the authors to proofread the document to correct the typos and harmonise the format. E.g. line 57, page 2, "ys"; page 18, the use of "- "or " _".

Response: The document has been proofread and typos were corrected.

6. Specific comment on figures

- I would highly recommend to improve the format of the figures. Furthermore, the size is not consistent among the different subsections of the same figure, e.g. see figure 3.

If comparing figure 7 and 8, they are also different size. I think this aspect need improvement.

Response: Thank you for the comment. The figures have been improved.

- Figure 1. Specify what does it mean the blue colour without mention to the countries (e.g. see the cell corresponding to aquaculture with other physical loss), I guess it means that this linkage appear in all assessed countries? In the figure, first line, appears "ACTIVITIES (REFERENCE)", I would recommend to include the reference in the reference list. Further, I would consider to change the name to table instead of figure as I think it is more a table than a figure.

Response: Thank you for the comment. The caption has been clarified. The blue colour depicts potential activities-pressures interactions, whereas the country codes indicate existing and assessed activities and the generated pressures in the MS. The reference has been included in the reference list, while the name has been changed to table instead of figure. Also add in the letter then that the blue colour is about present and assessed (the reviewer was asking about the non blue, the non-blue are not relevant as not assessed or as not existing)

- Figure 2. Here the name of the y axis appear as name of the graph, "% Total Risk".

Response: The elements of the chart have been corrected.

- Figure 6. The values that appear in the column are not very visible, some are overlapping with the lines. I would recommend to increase the size and black colour.
Response: We have decided not to include the charts on Posidonia oceanica originally numbered 6,7 and 8 in order to reduce the results section as suggested previously. Besides, relative information has been provided as Posidonia oceanica is part of the Infralittoral HardBiogenic BHT Aggregation.

- Figure 9. In the figure caption, I would include the description of the acronyms for the countries and also use the same format for the whole caption.

Response: The acronyms of the countries have been included. Part of the caption has been moved to the text, right below the figure.

- Regarding the colours for the figure, have you considered colour-blindness? In R there are specific palettes to make your figures accessible for colour-blind people.

Response: Thank you for the comment. Colours have been adapted accordingly.

Reviewer #2

The authors are presenting a very practical approach for EU Member States to establish priorities in terms of the descriptors that need the most policy and management attention in a regional sea. This paper is timely as it links assessment to policy. The following are some comments to be considered by the authors.

Line 11 Page 3: Could changes to hydrological conditions alter the movement and deposit of sediment and sands, thus altering the integrity of the seafloor? Could this be the case for the area being assessed in this paper?

Response: Indeed, this is the case and to identify areas where extensive and significant impacts may occur (depending on the activity, country and prevailing conditions prior to interventions that may alter the hydrological conditions that may in turn impact the seafloor integrity).

Line 52 Page 19: As I am reading through the figures, I have the impression that these are percent relative risk to each country. The use of "% Total Risk" is not clear to me and may need to be changed or described.

Response: The term has been clarified in the methodology section The methodology section were %Total Risk is mentioned was reworded and the definition of Total Risk was clarified (lines 201-206).

Line 35 Page 19: The MSFD 2008/56 provides definitions for environmental targets as policy benchmarks. These targets are to establish the desired conditions and specifications for good environmental status under the sovereignty or jurisdiction of Member States. As specified in MSFD 2017/848, pressure-based thresholds are used to assess the quality level achieved for a particular criterion in achieving good environmental status and could figure within a broad. In the last paragraph of the

discussion, Are the authors proposing that their methodology could be used to develop thresholds or could be used to set priorities for monitoring of such thresholds. I think there is an important aspect that the authors may be missing with their work where thresholds are used as a ranking of risk instead of prediction of impact.

Response: Thank you for this comment and helpful suggestion. Text has been added in the designated part and conclusions, as requested, to explain how the methodology can be aligned with policy requirements, therefore, providing more fit-for-purpose assessments of risk. (lines 547-570).

Theodora Paramana
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National and Kapodistrian University of Athens,
Athens, Greece.
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Tel: +30 6977296226/ +30 210 727 4724

January 15th, 2024

Dear Reviewers,

On behalf of my co-authors and me, please find enclosed our revised manuscript entitled 'Screening and assessing physical pressures affecting seafloor integrity in the Mediterranean region' submitted for consideration to Ocean & Coastal Management bearing the Manuscript Number OCMA-D-23-00541.

The authors contributed to the revision of the manuscript supporting that achieving a proper management of the marine environment, following the Ecosystem-based approach, requires accurate and thorough assessments of its environmental status, of the human activities and generated pressures that cause physical disturbance and loss of the seabed, while accounting for the strength of their interaction.

The manuscript has been revised in accordance with your comments and suggestions. We are really grateful for the time and effort you dedicated to the present work, as we believe that trying to address your comments, we have introduced amendments that have considerably improved the quality of the manuscript.

Please find below all the changes that have been made to the manuscript. My co-authors and I would like to thank you in advance for considering these alterations.

Yours faithfully,

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Responses to Reviewers

Reviewer #1

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MSCG: Commission Expert Group on Strategic Coordination for the MSFD
MSFD: Marine Strategy Framework Directive
MWE: Western Mediterranean Sea
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SL: Slovenia
TG Seabed: EU Technical group on seabed habitats and sea-floor integrity

- I would recommend the authors to proofread the document to correct the typos and harmonise the format. E.g. line 57, page 2, "ys"; page 18, the use of "- "or "_".
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Response: Thank you for this comment and helpful suggestion. Text has been added in the designated part and conclusions, as requested, to explain how the methodology can be aligned with policy requirements, therefore, providing more fit-for-purpose assessments of risk (lines 547-570).

Theodora Paramana
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Athens, Greece.
Email: tparaman@geol.uoa.gr
Tel: +30 6977296226/ +30 210 727 4724

January 15th, 2024

Dear Editors in Chief,

On behalf of my co-authors and me, please find enclosed our revised manuscript entitled 'Screening and assessing physical pressures affecting seafloor integrity in the Mediterranean region' submitted for consideration to *Ocean & Coastal Management* bearing the Manuscript Number OCMA-D-23-00541.

The present research article has been submitted by a group of researchers formed in the framework of ABIOMMED project [Support coherent and coordinated assessment of biodiversity and measures across Mediterranean for the next 6-year cycle of MSFD implementation] funded by the European Commission, DG Environment, under the Grant Agreement No 110661/2020/839620/SUB/ENV.C.2.

The authors contributed to the revision of the manuscript supporting that achieving a proper management of the marine environment, following the Ecosystem-based approach, requires accurate and thorough assessments of its environmental status, of the human activities and generated pressures that cause physical disturbance and loss of the seabed, while accounting for the strength of their interaction. Thus, we believe that our manuscript will be of interest to the readers of *Ocean & Coastal Management*.

The manuscript has been revised following the comments and suggestions made by the reviewers in the review process of the paper submission. We would like to thank the reviewers for the time and effort dedicated to the present work as we believe that trying to answer their comments and following their recommendations, we have introduced corresponding amendments that have considerably improved the quality of the manuscript.

Please find below all the changes that have been made to the manuscript following the reviewers' comments. My co-authors and I would like to thank you in advance for considering these alterations.

Yours faithfully,

Theodora Paramana

Responses to Reviewers

Reviewer #1

1. Methodology

- Lines 47-50, page 3, I would recommend to include information about why authors use 3 impact risk criteria instead of 5 to let the readers know the reasoning behind their choice.

Response: Thank you for this suggestion, we added text in the methodology explaining why (lines 158-161) and in the conclusions section supporting how this could be done in a second step after revision (lines 678-683).

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Response: The evidence sources are provided in the manuscript below Table 3 (lines 240-243).

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Response: Thank you for this comment. Please consider that TR is total risk. The methodology section mentioned was reworded and the definition of Total Risk was clarified (lines 201-206). To avoid confusion the terms used are Impact Risk (IR) and Total Risk (%TR) throughout the document. Furthermore, the description of the SPSS options (explore) used for analysis was also improved (lines 219-221).

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Response: The use of site footprint refers to the smallest footprint considered by the method as shown in Table 2. The sentence was rewritten for clarity.

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Response: The reference list has been amended accordingly.

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Response: The reference list has been amended to conform to the journal guidelines.

5. General comments

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Response: The changes have been made from capital letters to minor letters throughout the text for Abrasion, Sealing, Other physical disturbance, Other physical loss, Hydrological changes, Scoring Table.

However, activities and Broad Habitat Types words start with capital letter so they are noticeable in the text and avoid confusion.

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Response: Necessary corrections have been made throughout the document.

- I would recommend not having a space between the % symbol and the number. E.g. 12%. Throughout the text, in some places there is a space and in others not. Consistency is needed.

Response: All such cases have been corrected throughout the manuscript.

- I would use "MS" instead of "MSs" as it is the most used acronym for member states.

Response: Thank you for the suggestion. MS has been used throughout the document.

- It would be helpful to reduce the use of acronyms. If possible, it would be helpful also to include a list of acronyms.

Response: A list of acronyms has been included. Acronyms have been retained when referring to MS for reasons of space and when using directive terminology such as GES, MSFD.

List of acronyms

BHT: Broad Habitat Types

D6: Descriptor 6

DI: Degree of Impact

EO: Ecosystem Overviews

FO: Frequency of Occurrence

GES: Good Environmental Status

GR: Greece

HELCOM: Convention on the Protection of the Marine Environment of the Baltic Sea Area

HR: Croatia

ICES: International Council for the Exploration of the Sea.

IT: Italy

MAD: Adriatic Sea

MAL: Aegean-Levantine Sea

MIC: Ionian Sea and Central Mediterranean Sea

MS: Member State(s)

MSCG: Commission Expert Group on Strategic Coordination for the MSFD

MSFD: Marine Strategy Framework Directive

MWE: Western Mediterranean Sea

SE: Spatial Extent

SL: Slovenia

TG Seabed: EU Technical group on seabed habitats and sea-floor integrity

- I would recommend the authors to proofread the document to correct the typos and harmonise the format. E.g. line 57, page 2, "ys"; page 18, the use of "- "or " _".

Response: The document has been proofread and typos were corrected.

6. Specific comment on figures

- I would highly recommend to improve the format of the figures. Furthermore, the size is not consistent among the different subsections of the same figure, e.g. see figure 3. If comparing figure 7 and 8, they are also different size. I think this aspect need improvement.

Response: Thank you for the comment. The figures have been improved.

- Figure 1. Specify what does it mean the blue colour without mention to the countries (e.g. see the cell corresponding to aquaculture with other physical loss), I guess it means that this linkage appear in all assessed countries? In the figure, first line, appears "ACTIVITIES (REFERENCE)", I would recommend to include the reference in the reference list. Further, I would consider to change the name to table instead of figure as I think it is more a table than a figure.

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Response: The elements of the chart have been corrected.

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- Regarding the colours for the figure, have you considered colour-blindness? In R there are specific palettes to make your figures accessible for colour-blind people.

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Reviewer #2

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Theodora Paramana

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Line 52 Page 19: As I am reading through the figures, I have the impression that these are percent relative risk to each country. The use of "% Total Risk" is not clear to me and may need to be changed or described.

Response: The term has been clarified in the methodology section. The methodology section where %Total Risk is mentioned was reworded and the definition of Total Risk was clarified (lines 201-206).

Line 35 Page 19: The MSFD 2008/56 provides definitions for environmental targets as policy benchmarks. These targets are to establish the desired conditions and specifications for good environmental status under the sovereignty or jurisdiction of Member States. As specified in MSFD 2017/848, pressure-based thresholds are used to assess the quality level achieved for a particular criterion in achieving good environmental status and could figure within a broad. In the last paragraph of the discussion, Are the authors proposing that their methodology could be used to develop thresholds or could be used to set priorities for monitoring of such thresholds. I think there is an important aspect that the authors may be missing with their work where thresholds are used as a ranking of risk instead of prediction of impact.

Response: Thank you for this comment and helpful suggestion. Text has been added in the designated part and conclusions, as requested, to explain how the methodology can be aligned with policy requirements, therefore, providing more fit-for-purpose assessments of risk. (lines 547-570).

Highlights

- Screening and assessing physical pressures affecting seafloor integrity.
- Testing an exposure-effect methodology relevant to MSFD Descriptor 6.
- Addressing key physical pressures on benthic habitats in a harmonised way.
- Assisting decision makers in prioritizing management actions for the seafloor.
- Ecosystem-based management in the Mediterranean region.

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4 1 RESEARCH PAPER
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7 3 **Screening and assessing physical pressures affecting seafloor integrity**
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9 4 **in the Mediterranean region**
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39 32 **Abstract**

40 33 Ecosystem based management requires assessment of human activities and generated pressures that
41 34 cause physical disturbance and loss of the seabed within the Mediterranean, also accounting for the
42 35 strength of their interaction. To support the implementation of Descriptor 6 of the Marine Strategy
43 36 Framework Directive (MSFD), the present work aimed at testing the applicability of an exposure-effect
44 37 methodology and harmonizing - across countries sharing the same marine waters - the identification of
45 38 the MSFD key physical pressures on benthic habitats and their relative importance at different spatial
46 39 scales (national, subregional, regional) in the Mediterranean Sea. The methodology uses 24 MSFD
47 40 relevant human activities, five physical pressures, and 13 Broad Habitat Types (BHT). The links between
48 41 human activities, physical pressures and the different MSFD Broad Habitat Types affected are identified
49 42 and scored using three criteria; namely Spatial Extent, Frequency of Occurrence, and Degree of Impact.
50 43 The methodology assesses the risk of pressures in a semi-quantitative way, integrating both quantitative
51 44 (data) and qualitative (expert judgement) information, where quantitative data is not available, and allows
52 45 the ranking of the physical pressures affecting the seafloor. The methodology was applied in the marine
53 46 waters of Italy, Slovenia, Croatia and Greece. Abrasion (e.g., related to fishing or boating) and sealing (e.g.,
54 caused by structures) were ranked as top pressures; the former is widespread over different BHTs, in a

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47 persistent manner and presents intense impacts; the latter appears locally, at specific sites, and
48 persistently, generating an acute impact. According to the results, the infralittoral and circalittoral habitats
49 are those most affected by physical pressures. The identification of major pressures can assist
50 considerably towards the elimination or mitigation of the impacts through actions on the human activities,
51 as it enables the prioritisation of tailor-made measures to achieve or maintain the Good Environmental
52 Status (GES) in the region.

53 **Keywords:** seafloor integrity, risk assessment, human activities, impact, MSFD, ecosystem-based
54 management, Mediterranean Sea

56 **List of acronyms**

- 57 BHT: Broad Habitat Types
- 58 D6: Descriptor 6
- 59 DI: Degree of Impact
- 60 EO: Ecosystem Overviews
- 61 FO: Frequency of Occurrence
- 62 GES: Good Environmental Status
- 63 GR: Greece
- 64 HELCOM: Convention on the Protection of the Marine Environment of the Baltic Sea Area
- 65 HR: Croatia
- 66 ICES: International Council for the Exploration of the Sea.
- 67 IT: Italy
- 68 MAD: Adriatic Sea
- 69 MAL: Aegean-Levantine Sea
- 70 MIC: Ionian Sea and Central Mediterranean Sea
- 71 MS: Member State(s)
- 72 MSCG: Commission Expert Group on Strategic Coordination for the MSFD
- 73 MSFD: Marine Strategy Framework Directive
- 74 MWE: Western Mediterranean Sea
- 75 SE: Spatial Extent
- 76 SL: Slovenia
- 77 TG Seabed: EU Technical group on seabed habitats and sea-floor integrity

79 **1. Introduction**

80 All anthropogenic marine activities have a footprint on the marine environment which generates
81 pressures. If these activities are not moderated, they will create pressures and impacts on the natural and
82 human systems (Elliot et al., 2018; Elliot et al., 2021). The seabed provides humans with invaluable
83 ecosystem services, such as food, raw materials, and energy provisioning. The number of sectors that
84 exploit the marine environment and its resources is significant, leading to numerous interacting pressures
85 (Knights et al., 2013) which alter the geological, physical, and chemical conditions of the seafloor, and
86 affect the seabed and the benthic communities (ICES, 2019). The European marine regions are all under
87 high levels of pressures due to multiple, overlapping uses from human activities which vary regionally.
88 Analysing the spatial distribution of pressures resulting from human activities can inform us about the
89 potential effects we exert on the marine environment (Korpinen et al., 2019).

90 To link human activities to the marine environment while assisting management decision-making, it is
91 necessary to adopt a flexible, problem-solving approach which succeeds in highlighting the interrelations
92 across sectors, activities, pressures, and ecosystem components (Knights et al., 2015). Management based
93 on a cause-consequence-response framework enables actions at various levels, i.e., local, national,
94 regional, and international (Cormier et al., 2022). In Ecosystem-based Management, a risk assessment

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95 process can describe the consequences and likelihood of an event, and can be used to identify, analyse,
96 and evaluate risks (Cormier and Lonsdale, 2020).

97 Under Descriptor 6 (D6), the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) requires that seafloor integrity
98 is at a level that ensures the structure and functions of the ecosystems are maintained, and benthic
99 ecosystems are not adversely affected (EU, 2008). The D6 Criteria (C) set by Commission Decision (EU)
100 2017/848 need the assessment of the spatial extent and distribution of physical loss (criteria D6C1/D6C4)
101 and disturbance (criteria D6C2/ D6C3) that pressures exert on the seafloor and the assessment of the
102 status of each MSFD Broad Habitat Type (BHT). These assessments are expected to take place at the level
103 of Member State (MS), subregion and marine region (EC, 2017b).

104 Physical disturbance is caused by activities that directly perturbate benthic habitats without permanently
105 altering the type of the benthic substrate, provided that recovery to the original state can be achieved
106 given enough time (ICES, 2019). Numerous human activities may impact the seabed, directly or indirectly,
107 such as abrasion (scraping of the substrate by benthic trawling and benthic biota exploitation, propellers
108 of maritime traffic), alteration of the benthic conditions due to increased sedimentation or reduction of
109 light penetration, sedimentation caused by dredging, sediment disposal, demersal fishing gear, and
110 construction works. Benthic disturbance is rather high in the European waters with 23% of the assessed
111 area impacted (Korpinen et al., 2019). At a regional level, the Baltic seabed is more disturbed than other
112 regions (79%), followed by the Mediterranean Sea (69%), the Black Sea (55%), and the North East Atlantic
113 (44%) (Korpinen et al., 2019). Nevertheless, according to HELCOM, only 40% of the Baltic Sea is disturbed
114 (Helsinki Commission, 2018).

115 Physical loss refers to any human-induced permanent alteration of the physical habitat where recovery is
116 impossible without additional intervention or where recovery would take too much time (typically more
117 than 12 years, as proposed by TGSeabed). There are three types of loss (ICES, 2019): i) sealing, i.e., the
118 capping of the original substrate with structures placed in the marine environment (e.g. wind turbines,
119 port infrastructure, metal pilings) or substrates that seal off the seabed and change the physical habitat
120 resulting in loss (e.g. rock or stone fills); ii) unsealed physical loss, i.e., permanent seabed habitat changes
121 (e.g. caused by dredge disposal or aggregate extraction); iii) loss of biogenic habitat, entailing historical
122 loss of biogenic habitats. Activities causing physical loss are construction over the seabed, extraction of
123 sand and gravel, capital dredging of the seabed, removal of hard substrate or biogenic reefs, disposing of
124 waste material and dredged matter. In terms of the extent of habitat lost at the regional level, the greatest
125 habitat loss has occurred in the Baltic Sea (14% of the assessment units), followed by the Mediterranean
126 Sea (3.7%), the North East Atlantic (2%) and the Black Sea (1.5%) (Korpinen et al., 2019).

127 Changes in hydrological conditions (MSFD Descriptor 7) are also relevant to seafloor integrity as they may
128 affect seabed habitats and the prevailing conditions on the seafloor (EU, 2008). The changes in
129 hydrological conditions involve altered water regimes, salinity, seawater temperature, or even water
130 renewal time and can be caused by coastal and offshore structures. Salinity is also affected by altered
131 freshwater inputs and water extraction. Regarding temperature, it can be increased locally in the vicinity
132 of warm water outflows from power and other coastal industrial plants. Water renewal time may in turn
133 affect the salinity and temperature of a coastal area. About 14–16% of the coastal area in the
134 Mediterranean and the Baltic Sea, 6% of the North East Atlantic, and 3% of the Black Sea are impacted by
135 changes in hydrological conditions (Korpinen et al., 2019).

136 To achieve the MSFD goals regarding the protection of the seabed, it is essential to foster the adoption of
137 a common regional/subregional approach towards a consistent assessment of the status of benthic
138 habitats subjected to human activities and pressures. This will contribute to the establishment of
139 coordinated regional measures to protect sea-floor integrity, in particular benthic habitats, and
140 communities, from pressures. Hence, the identification of the key human pressures responsible for
141 physical loss and disturbance is a vital element in this process.

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In this perspective, and in the framework of the European ABIOMMED project (Support coherent and coordinated assessment of biodiversity and measures across Mediterranean for the next 6-year cycle of MSFD implementation, No 110661/2020/839620/SUB/ENV.C.2), the present work has a two-fold aim: i) to assess the impact of various human activities and their manifested pressures on the benthic habitats and to rank identified pressures in Italy, Croatia, Slovenia, and Greece and ii) to develop and test a harmonised methodology of risk assessment of pressures on benthic habitats to be applied at national, subregional and regional scale, adopting the exposure-effect approach. The physical pressure types examined within the assessment are physical disturbance, namely abrasion and other physical disturbance of the seabed (e.g., smothering, siltation), and physical loss, namely sealing and other physical loss (e.g. extraction).

2. Methodology

To identify MSFD Descriptor 6 relevant pressures and human activities present in the Mediterranean area, at different scales (e.g., national, subregional), two existing risk assessment methodologies were considered and integrated: the exposure-effect approach for evaluating ecosystem-wide risks from human activities by Knights et al. (Knights et al., 2015) as well as the Ecosystem Overviews approach (EO) developed by ICES (ICES, 2021b). Therefore, the suggested methodology uses three impact risk criteria, Spatial Extent, Frequency of Occurrence, Degree of Impact, as it is suggested by Knights et al. (2015) and in the Ecosystem Overviews approach, since they are considered adequate to identify and evaluate activity-pressure-ecological component pathways. The criteria of persistence and resilience which are further used by Knights et al. (2015) are not considered as they would require a certain review and alignment of the scales. The methodology allows to integrate in the assessment information coming from different sources, i.e., data, literature, and expert judgement. To frame the approach, the adopted methodology was fully aligned with the terms and definitions of the MSFD, following Directive 2017/845 (EC, 2017a) and Commission decision 2017/848 (EC, 2017b) and using the latest MSFD guidance (EC, 2022). To serve the ABIOMMED project purposes, the methodology was applied to Descriptor 6, at Broad Habitat Type (BHT) level. In this perspective, several steps were taken, as detailed below.

1) Step A-Human Activities & Pressures matrix development: An activities-pressures matrix was developed for Member States (MS) including all human activities generating specific pressures in their marine waters. Originally, the matrix included all MSFD activities and pressures as listed in Directive 2017/845, ANNEX III, Tables 2a & 2b (EC, 2017a). However, to screen the activities compromising seafloor integrity in more detail and to be able to prioritize relevant measures, there was a focus on Descriptor 6 relevant activities, while only physical pressures were included in the matrix, i.e., abrasion, other physical disturbance, sealing, other physical loss, changes to hydrological conditions (Figure 1). In the matrix, the interactions between activities and pressures were indicated, irrespectively of the scale of operation and in some cases even with complete lack of spatial data, based on the knowledge of the marine environment and the expert judgement of the ABIOMMED project research members.

2) Step B-Identification of linkage chains: The identification of the links between activities, pressures and the different ecosystem components impacted by these pressures led to the establishment of the linkage chains. For the present assessment, the considered components are the MSFD Broad Habitat Types (BHT), aggregated for the different benthic zones (Table 1). Overall, 24 D6 relevant activities, five pressures and 13 MSFD BHT, therefore, 1560 linkage chains (human activity-pressure-BHT) were created.

3) Step C-Risk assessment: To evaluate the identified linkage chains a scoring table was developed including Knights et al. (2015) pressure assessment criteria Spatial Extent, Frequency of Occurrence, and Degree of Impact (Table 2) and the 1560 linkage chains. The chains were evaluated against the criteria based on GIS data (Italy, Slovenia) using available average data from 2015 to 2021 according to availability, on literature (Greece, Slovenia), and on expert judgement (Croatia, Greece, Italy, Slovenia) (Table 3), while the evidence for the evaluation was documented on the scoring table, indicating 1 for qualitative

judgement, 2 for literature support, and 3 for data support for each chain. For example, the assessment of sealing impact was performed using the mapping of structures from permits and licenses in national databases or published literature, while to quantify abrasion from demersal fishing the Swept Area Ratio (SAR) analysis was used from vessel satellite tracking (VMS or AIS) (national country data and published literature e.g. Smith et al. 2023). Following the aggregation level of the data used, the assessment was performed at national level for Slovenia, Croatia and Greece, with the latter integrating information from three marine subregions, i.e., Adriatic Sea (MAD), Ionian Sea and Central Mediterranean Sea (MIC), Aegean Levantine Sea (MAL), whereas for Italy, the risk assessment was performed per subregion, i.e., Adriatic Sea (MAD), Ionian and Central Mediterranean Sea (MIC), Western Mediterranean Sea (MWE). The impact risk scores were calculated in an Excel scoring table to enable the identification of top risks/pressures. The Impact Risk (IR) score per linkage chain was calculated as the result of the scores assigned to the three criteria, i.e., Spatial Extent (SE) multiplied by Frequency of Occurrence (FO) multiplied by the Degree of Impact (DI).

$$IR = SE * FO * DI \quad (\text{Knights et al., 2015})$$

4) *Step D-Pressure ranking*: For each linkage chain, the Impact Risk (IR) score was rescaled as a percentage of the summed Impact Risk of all chains, producing the Total Risk (%TR) of each chain. Linkage chains with Total Risk higher than 1% were identified as presenting significant risk, while the chains presenting the five highest Total Risk values were considered as the most critical risks deemed relevant for management action. The analysis assumes that the higher the Total Risk the greater the threat to the environment and the component in question caused by the pressure. As a result, pressures were ranked based on the Total Risk of the linkage chains.

Two rounds of scoring were conducted for each ABIOMMED MS by the authors, to reduce inconsistencies in the application of the methodology, with a consolidation process guiding the scoring phase assessment. These results were weighted, based on the extent of the habitat type in question in relation to the overall extent of the MS seafloor referenced through EUSeaMap 2019 (Vasquez, et al., 2015). The use of weights reduced distortions both at the national or subregional level. The analysis considered only submerged habitats since littoral is not present in EUSeaMap 2019 for the Italian waters. Additionally, to achieve consistency among MS, the assessments were conducted based on the same rationale, having a common approach to the potential extent of activities and their degree of impact. Therefore, the scoring of the criteria ensured that the national information, quantitative or qualitative, was integrated in the assessment in a compatible way and conclusions could be deducted both at national and broader scales. The pressures were ranked following the 2nd assessment round results, and it identified which pressures pose the greatest threat to the ecosystem. The results were statistically analysed with IBM SPSS Software 17.0. The Explore option of SPSS was applied to Total Risk (%TR) with activities, pressures and BHT serving as analysing factors, in order to produce descriptive statistics (mean, median, range) and boxplot graphs.

Table 1: MSFD Broad Habitat Type (BHT) aggregations used in risk assessment and pressure ranking.

BENTHIC ZONE	BHT AGGREGATIONS
Littoral	Hard / Firm (Rock_ Biogenic)
Littoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)
Infralittoral	Hard / Firm (Rock/ Biogenic)
Infralittoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)
Circalittoral	Hard / Firm (Rock_ Biogenic)
Circalittoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)
Offshore Circalittoral	Hard / Firm (Rock_ Biogenic)
Offshore Circalittoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)
Upper bathyal	Hard / Firm (Rock_ Biogenic)
Upper bathyal	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)

Lower bathyal	Hard / Firm (Rock_ Biogenic)	226
Lower bathyal	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)	227
Abyssal	Hard_Soft	228
		229

230 Table 2: Pressure assessment criteria and numerical risk scores, following Knights et al. (2015).

Criteria	Categories	Estimation		Score
Spatial Extent	Widespread (overlap $\geq 50\%$)	75	Percentage of overlap	1.00
	Local (overlap $>5\%$ & $<50\%$)	27.5		0.37
	Site (overlap $>0\%$ & $<5\%$)	2.5		0.03
Frequency	Persistent (pressure throughout the year)	12	Months per year	1.00
	Common (pressure up to 8 months per year)	8		0.67
	Occasional (pressure up to 4 months per year)	4		0.33
	Rare (pressure up to 1 month per year)	1		0.08
Degree of Impact	Acute (severe effects after 1 interaction)	1	Severity of interaction	1.00
	Chronic (severe effects after 8 interactions)	0.125		0.13
	Low (severe effect not expected after 100 interactions)	0.01		0.01

231 Table 3: The evidence sources used by MS experts for the application of the assessment criteria.
232

	Criteria Evidence Sources		
	Spatial Extent	Frequency of Occurrence	Degree of Impact
Greece	data/qualitative	data/qualitative	data/qualitative/ literature
Croatia	qualitative	qualitative	qualitative
Slovenia	data/qualitative	data	data/qualitative/ literature
Italy_MAD	data	data	qualitative
Italy_MIC	data	data	qualitative
Italy_MWE	data	data	qualitative

233 The evidence sources for the different MS included regional reports with national information on activities
234 and pressures, national country data, and published literature: UNEP/MAP & SPA/RAC, 2021; UNEP/MAP
235 & Plan Bleu, 2020; Connor et al., 2023 a & b; Smith et al., 2023, Sala et al. 2023; Tsikopoulou et al., 2022;
236 Piante & Ody, 2015, Knights et al., 2015; Micheli et al., 2013, HCMR, 2020; HCMR, 2019; YPEN 2018.
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238 3. Results

239 3.1 Activity-Pressure Matrix

240 The activities-pressures matrices produced by each of the project MS (Croatia, Greece Italy, Slovenia) are
241 presented in an integrated matrix (Table 4). The blue coloured cells indicate the activities identified as
242 causing specific pressures, whereas in those blue cells the countries reporting the specific activity taking
243 place in their marine waters and consequently the specific pressure generated are included.
244 Whilst a common pattern emerges, the comparison among matrices shows different activities taking place
245 in each MS. For instance, experts identified the presence of 17 activities occurring in the marine
246 environment of Greece, 12 in Italy, 13 in Slovenia and 18 in Croatia. Moreover, the pressures attributed
247 to these activities present slight differences, possibly showing a different rationale in the way the
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249 pressures are associated to each activity and their potential impact (e.g., negligible vs not negligible
250 pressure) among MS. Fish and shellfish harvesting (professional, recreational) demersal, and Transport-
251 shipping are activities taking place in all MS and they are related to abrasion, while Transport-
252 infrastructure is present in all MS and related to sealing. Land Claim and Canalisation are identified in the
253 coastal environment of Slovenia and Croatia but not in Greece and Italy. Renewable energy production
254 constitutes a relatively new sector in the Mediterranean therefore only existing in Italy and is related to
255 sealing. Finally, some activities are not at all reported by Italy, such as small-scale fishing, tourism and
256 leisure, urban and industrial uses because the littoral benthic zone was not assessed in the Italian
257 assessment areas due to lack of data.

259 Table 4: Activities-pressures matrix for ABIOMMED project MS. The blue colour depicts potential
260 activities-pressures interactions, whereas the country codes indicate existing and assessed activities and
261 the generated pressures in the MS. GR: Greece, HR: Croatia, IT: Italy, and SI: Slovenia

			PHYSICAL PRESSURES				
			Physical disturbance to seabed (temporary or reversible)		Physical loss (due to permanent change of seabed substrate or morphology and to extraction of seabed substrate)		Changes to hydrological conditions
			Abrasion	Other physical disturbance	Sealing	Other physical loss	
ACTIVITIES (MSFD 2017/845_ANNEX III_ Table 2b)	Physical restructuring of rivers, coastline or seabed (water management)	Land claim			HR, SI		
		Canalisation & other watercourse modifications			HR, SI	SI	
		Coastal defence & flood protection			GR, IT, SI	SI	SI
		Offshore structures (other than for oil/gas/renewables)			IT		
		Restructuring of seabed morphology including dredging, and depositing of materials	GR, IT, HR	GR, IT, HR			HR, SI
	Extraction of non-living resources	Extraction of minerals (rock, metal ores, gravel, sand, shell)			GR, IT, HR		
		Extraction of oil and gas, including infrastructure			HR, SI	GR, HR, SI	HR, SI
		Extraction of salt			GR		
	Production of energy	Renewable energy generation (wind, wave and tidal power), including infrastructure			IT		
		Non-renewable energy generation					
		Transmission of electricity and communications (cables)			GR, IT, HR		
	Extraction of living resources	Fish and shellfish harvesting (professional, recreational)	Demersal trawling	GR, IT, HR, SI	GR, HR, SI		HR, SI
			Dredging	IT, HR	HR		HR
			Small scale	GR, HR, SI	GR, HR		HR
	Cultivation of living resources	Aquaculture – marine, including infrastructure			GR, IT	GR, HR	HR, SI
		Transport infrastructure				GR, IT, HR, SI	HR, SI
	Transport	Transport – shipping			GR, IT, HR, SI	GR, HR, SI	
		Urban uses			GR, HR	GR, HR	HR
	Urban and industrial uses	Industrial uses				GR, HR	
		Waste treatment and disposal			GR, HR, SI	GR, HR, SI	
		Tourism & leisure infrastructure				GR, HR, SI	HR, SI
	Tourism & leisure	Tourism & leisure activities			GR, HR, SI	GR, HR, SI	
		Military operations			GR, IT	GR	GR, HR

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4 **263 3.2 Risk assessment outcomes**

5 264 The risk assessment showed that in most cases the Spatial Extent of abrasion, sealing, other physical
6 265 disturbance, other physical loss, hydrological changes were assessed as site, i.e., overlapping between 0
7 266 and <5% with an ecological component. Only Greece assessed abrasion as spatially widespread (overlap
8 267 >50%) for some activity-pressure combinations, and Slovenia as local (overlap up to 50%). Regarding
9 268 Frequency, sealing was assessed as persistent by all MS, while abrasion was assessed as rare (HR,
10 269 IT_MAD_MIC_MWE), occasional (SI, IT_MWE), and common (GR). Other physical disturbance was
11 270 assessed as either occasional (GR, SI), common (IT_MIC), or persistent (HR, IT_MAD, IT_MWE). Other
12 271 physical loss was evaluated as rare (HR, IT_MAD, IT_MWE) and persistent (SI, HR). Changes to hydrological
13 272 conditions were assessed as permanent (SI). As far as the Degree of Impact is concerned, abrasion was
14 273 evaluated as acute (GR, HR, IT_MAD, IT_MIC, IT_MWE) and chronic (GR). Sealing was assessed as acute
15 274 by all MS. Other physical disturbance was assessed as low (GR, HR) and chronic (SI, IT_MAD, IT_MIC,
16 275 IT_MWE). Other physical loss was evaluated as low (HR, IT_MAD, IT_MWE) and chronic (SI). Finally,
17 276 changes to hydrological conditions were assessed as chronic (SI).

18 277 Focusing on the activities-pressures relationship, Greece and Italy_MIC identified only abrasion, sealing
19 278 and other physical disturbance as pressures generated from the human activities in their marine waters,
20 279 whereas Croatia, Italy_MAD and Italy_MWE additionally identified other physical loss. Slovenia was the
21 280 only MS which identified all five physical pressures caused by current activities. Abrasion was the most
22 281 intense pressure in Italy (in all assessment areas) and Greece, whereas sealing was the most intense
23 282 pressure in Croatia. In Slovenia, sealing slightly outweighed abrasion (Figure 1).

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284 Figure 1: Total Risk (%TR) of pressures assessed. MAD: Adriatic Sea; MIC: Ionian Sea and Central
285 Mediterranean Sea; MWE: Western Mediterranean Sea.

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287 All MS attributed abrasion to Fish and shellfish harvesting (professional, recreational) demersal, and Fish
288 and shellfish harvesting (professional, recreational) small scale as well as to Tourism and leisure activities
289 (except IT_MIC). Greece, Slovenia, and Croatia also acknowledged Restructuring of seabed morphology
290 including dredging and depositing of materials, and Transport-shipping as generators of abrasion. Military
291 operations were also mentioned (GR, HR) as well as Fish and shellfish harvesting (professional,
292 recreational) dredging (IT_MAD) (Figure 2a).

293 Sealing was attributed by all MS to Transport infrastructure. Coastal defence and flood protection was
294 acknowledged as a generator of sealing for all MS apart from Croatia, Tourism and leisure infrastructure
295 by all apart from Italy_MIC, Transmission of electricity and communications (cables, pipelines) and
296 Extraction of oil and gas, including infrastructure by all except Slovenia. Several other activities were
297 alleged to generate sealing; Land claim (SI, HR), Canalisation & other watercourse modifications (HR),
298 Offshore structures (other than for oil/gas/renewables) (IT_MAD, IT_MIC, IT_MWE), Restructuring of

seabed morphology including dredging and depositing of materials (HR), Aquaculture-marine including infrastructure (GR, SI, HR), Waste treatment & disposal (SI, HR), Military Operations (GR, HR) (Figure 2b). Other physical disturbance was attributed to Aquaculture-marine, including infrastructure by all MS. Transmission of electricity and communications (cables) were acknowledged as generators of other physical pressures by all MS except Slovenia, and Tourism and leisure activities by all MS apart from Italy_MIC. Transport-shipping is acknowledged by Greece, Slovenia, Croatia, and Italy_MWE, while Fish and shellfish harvesting demersal by Greece, Slovenia and Croatia. Other physical disturbance was also attributed to several activities; Restructuring of seabed morphology including dredging and depositing of materials (GR, HR, IT_MAD), Extraction of oil and gas including infrastructure (GR, IT_MAD, IT_MWE), Waste treatment and disposal (GR, SI, HR), Coastal defence & flood protection (GR, SI), Fish and shellfish harvesting (professional, recreational) small scale (GR, HR), Military operations (GR, HR), Canalisation & other watercourse modifications (SI), as well as Transport infrastructure (SI) (Figure 2c). Other physical loss was identified only by Slovenia, Croatia and IT_MWE. Slovenia attributed other physical loss to Coastal defence & flood protection, Restructuring of seabed morphology including dredging and depositing of material, Fish and shellfish harvesting (professional, recreational) demersal, Aquaculture-marine including infrastructure, Transport infrastructure, and Tourism and leisure infrastructure. Croatia acknowledged Restructuring of seabed morphology including dredging and depositing of material, and Aquaculture-marine, including infrastructure as generators of other physical loss, whereas IT_MWE attributed it to Military operations only. Finally, hydrological changes were identified by Slovenia only and were attributed to Transport infrastructure.

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Figure 2: Total Risk (%TR) of abrasion (a), sealing (b), other physical disturbance (c) generated by the activities assessed.

3.3 Pressure Ranking

The risk assessment results provided for the ranking of the pressures generated by human activities. In the analysis the linkage chains having a Total Impact Risk >0.5% were considered, however, only those

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340 having a Total Risk (%TR) >1% were highlighted as significant pressures. Furthermore, the linkage chains
341 with the five highest Total Risk (%TR) values were identified as major pressures and were used for ranking
342 the key pressures for all MS (Table 5). In Greece, 22 linkage chains had a Total Risk ranging between 0.55
343 and 35.8%, with 12 exceeding 1%. Croatia had 28 linkage chains with a Total Risk ranging from 0.61 to
344 10.26%, of which 24 exceeded 1%. For Slovenia, 18 linkage chains were considered with a Total Risk in the
345 range from 0.50 to 15.94%, of which 14 exceeded 1%. In Italy_MAD, 19 linkage chains had a Total Risk
346 ranging from 0.60 to 40.65%, with 15 exceeding 1%. Italy_MIC had 13 linkage chains with Total Risk values
347 between 0.72 and 22.50%, of which 10 exceeded 1%. In Italy_MWE, the ranking process identified 10
348 linkage chains with a Total Risk ranging from 2.50 to 55.90%, all exceeding 1%.

349 The ranking of the linkage chains for all MS showed that abrasion generated by Fish and shellfish
350 harvesting (professional, recreational) demersal occupied the top risk places and, thus, poses the greatest
351 threat to the marine environment impacting most of the habitats, but mainly Circalittoral, Offshore
352 Circalittoral and Upper bathyal soft sediments. Abrasion generated by Transport-shipping were identified
353 by Greece and Slovenia (ranked in the 3rd and 5th place accordingly), while abrasion attributed to Fish and
354 shellfish harvesting (professional, recreational) small scale was ranked in the 1st place in Slovenia.

355 Sealing is ranked in the top 5 by all MS, generated by Canalisation & other watercourse modifications
356 (ranked 4th in HR), Coastal defence & flood protection (ranked 3rd in SI and 4th in IT_MAD), Extraction of
357 oil and gas, including infrastructure (ranked in the 4th and 5th places in HR and IT_MAD respectively).
358 Sealing caused by Military operations, Offshore structures (other than for oil/gas/renewables), Renewable
359 energy generation (wind, wave and tidal power), including infrastructure, Transmission of electricity and
360 communications (cables) was ranked in the top 5 pressures by Croatia and Italy_MAD_MIC. Sealing was
361 also attributed to Aquaculture – marine, including infrastructure (HR, SI, IT_MIC), while ranked in the 2nd
362 place in Slovenia. Finally, sealing attributed to Transport infrastructure, Tourism and leisure infrastructure,
363 and Waste treatment and disposal was identified in the top 5 places by Greece, Croatia, Slovenia, and
364 Italy_MAD (Table 5).

365 Other physical disturbance from Extraction of oil and gas, including infrastructure was identified by
366 Italy_MAD, ranked 3rd and 4th for Circalittoral and Offshore circalittoral BHT respectively. For Greece and
367 Slovenia, other physical disturbance generated by Transport-shipping was ranked in the 3rd and 5th place
368 accordingly. Finally, other physical disturbance, and other physical loss were attributed to Aquaculture –
369 marine, including infrastructure (HR, SI, IT_MIC) and ranked in the 4th place.

370 At the subregional level, in the Adriatic Sea subregion including Croatia, Slovenia and Italy_MAD, there
371 was a total of 39 linkage chains depicting the top five pressures, whose Total Risk values ranged from 1.13
372 to 40.65%.

373 The overall highest Total Risk values were attributed to abrasion in Italy, whereas in Croatia to sealing. In
374 Slovenia, abrasion and sealing may impact the benthic habitats to an almost equal extent. Abrasion
375 occupied the top 3 places (1st, 2nd, 3rd for IT_MAD, 1st for SI and 1st, 3rd for HR). Abrasion caused by Fish
376 and shellfish harvesting (professional, recreational) small scale was the top pressure in Slovenia, impacting
377 Circalittoral Soft sediments. Additionally, the Total Risk from other physical disturbance was slightly lower.
378 Notably, despite the significantly lower Total Risk values for sealing in the Italian Adriatic, the number of
379 sealing chains scored was higher than those of abrasion, i.e., 29 vs 16. If all the fishing related pressures,
380 which were extremely high, were excluded from the analysis, the Total Risk would be 0.83% for abrasion
381 and 18.20% for sealing. Thus, in some habitats, smaller scale sealing may also be of some concern in the
382 Italian Adriatic. Other physical disturbance and other physical loss attributed to Fish and shellfish
383 harvesting (professional, recreational) demersal are among the top 5 pressures in Croatia and Slovenia,
384 ranked 3rd and 4th respectively. Finally, hydrological changes were only identified by Slovenia caused by
385 Transport Infrastructure, impacting Infralittoral Hard_Soft substrates.

387 Table 5: Top 5 linkage chains ranking for all MS with Total Risk (%TR) values indicated. Ranks indicated with background shading, from darkest
 388 (rank 1) to lightest (rank 5).

ACTIVITIES	PRESSURES	BENTHIC ZONES	BROAD HABITAT TYPES	GR	HR	SI	IT_MAD	IT_MIC	IT_MWE	
				RANK / % TOTAL RISK						
Fish and shellfish harvesting (professional, recreational)_DEMERSAL	Abrasion	Infralittoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)					1.18		
Fish and shellfish harvesting (professional, recreational)_DEMERSAL	Abrasion	Circalittoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)	10.11		15.94	40.65	10.99	5.6	
Fish and shellfish harvesting (professional, recreational)_DEMERSAL	Abrasion	Offshore Circalittoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)	6.44	10.26		25.16	6.63	5.5	
Fish and shellfish harvesting (professional, recreational)_DEMERSAL	Abrasion	Upper bathyal	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)	35.80	5.58		9.61	22.50	10.2	
Fish and shellfish harvesting (professional, recreational)_DEMERSAL	Abrasion	Upper bathyal	Hard/ Firm (Rock_Biogenic)					22.50	55.9	
Fish and shellfish harvesting (professional, recreational)_DEMERSAL	Other physical disturbance	Circalittoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)			15.94				
Fish and shellfish harvesting (professional, recreational)_DEMERSAL	Other physical disturbance	Offshore Circalittoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)		10.26					
Fish and shellfish harvesting (professional, recreational)_DEMERSAL	Other physical disturbance	Upper bathyal	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)		5.58					
Fish and shellfish harvesting (professional, recreational)_DEMERSAL	Other physical loss	Circalittoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)			1.93				
Fish and shellfish harvesting (professional, recreational)_SMALL SCALE	Abrasion	Circalittoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)			15.94				
Aquaculture – marine, including infrastructure	Sealing	Circalittoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)		5.24	14.84				
Aquaculture – marine, including infrastructure	Other physical disturbance	Circalittoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)			1.93				
Aquaculture – marine, including infrastructure	Other physical disturbance	Upper bathyal	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)					5.53		
Aquaculture – marine, including infrastructure	Other physical loss	Circalittoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)			1.93				
Canalisation & other watercourse modifications	Sealing	Circalittoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)		5.24					
Coastal defence & flood protection	Sealing	Infralittoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)	4.83		3.87				
Coastal defence & flood protection	Sealing	Circalittoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)				1.82			
Extraction of oil and gas, including infrastructure	Sealing	Circalittoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)				1.82			
Extraction of oil and gas, including infrastructure	Sealing	Offshore Circalittoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)		3.54		1.13			
Extraction of oil and gas, including infrastructure	Sealing	Upper bathyal	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)					5.53		
Extraction of oil and gas, including infrastructure	Other physical disturbance	Circalittoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)				1.82			
Extraction of oil and gas, including infrastructure	Other physical disturbance	Offshore Circalittoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)				1.13			
Military operations	Sealing	Circalittoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)		5.24					
Military operations	Sealing	Offshore Circalittoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)		3.54					
Military operations	Sealing	Upper bathyal	Hard/ Firm (Rock_Biogenic)		7.68					
Offshore structures (other than for oil/gas/renewables)	Sealing	Circalittoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)				1.82			
Offshore structures (other than for oil/gas/renewables)	Sealing	Offshore Circalittoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)				1.13			
Offshore structures (other than for oil/gas/renewables)	Sealing	Upper bathyal	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)					5.53		
Renewable energy generation (wind, wave and tidal power), including infrastructure	Sealing	Circalittoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)				1.82			
Renewable energy generation (wind, wave and tidal power), including infrastructure	Sealing	Offshore Circalittoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)				1.13			
Transmission of electricity and communications (cables)	Sealing	Circalittoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)		5.24		1.82			
Transmission of electricity and communications (cables)	Sealing	Offshore Circalittoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)		3.54		1.13			
Transmission of electricity and communications (cables)	Sealing	Upper bathyal	Hard/ Firm (Rock_Biogenic)					5.53		
Transmission of electricity and communications (cables)	Sealing	Upper bathyal	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)					5.53		
Transmission of electricity and communications (cables)	Other physical disturbance	Upper bathyal	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)						4.013	
Transport – shipping	Abrasion	Circalittoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)	7.60		1.83				RANK
Transport – shipping	Other physical disturbance	Circalittoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)			1.83				1
Transport infrastructure	Sealing	Infralittoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)	4.83						2
Transport infrastructure	Sealing	Circalittoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)				1.82			3
Tourism and leisure infrastructure	Sealing	Infralittoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)	4.83						4
Waste treatment and disposal	Sealing	Circalittoral	Soft (Coarse_Mixed_Sand_Mud)		5.24	14.84				5

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3.4 Descriptive statistics

The assessment results were statistically analysed, considering the linkage chains that contribute $\geq 0.1\%$ to the Total Risk for an improved illustration. Regarding the various activities, it was apparent that Fish and shellfish harvesting (professional, recreational) demersal was the most impacting activity in all MS. The higher Total Risk values were noted in the Italian subregions, both in terms of highest median and higher range of values (Figure 5).

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Figure 5: Distribution of Total Risk (%) grouped by activity for MS (a) depicting all activities (b) excluding fishing activities for better representation of the other activities.

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400 In the boxplots, the middle lines correspond to the median values; hinge lengths (end of box) represent
 401 the 25% quartiles from the median; whiskers represent the 1.5 times interquartile range (IQR) beyond the
 402 hinge. Outlier and extreme Total Risk (TR) values are also presented; outliers as black dots, which
 403 correspond to cases that fall more than 1.5 box lengths from the lower or upper hinge and indicate intense
 404 presence of human activities generating pressures; extremes as asterisks, which correspond to cases that
 405 fall more than 3 box lengths from the lower or upper hinge.
 406 Concerning the comparison of pressures among countries, abrasion presented the highest outlier values
 407 in Greece and the Italian assessment areas. In Croatia and Slovenia, the outliers for abrasion, sealing and
 408 other physical disturbance were similar in magnitude. The highest non outlier value range (largest box)
 409 for sealing was in Croatia and Italy_MAD. In the case of abrasion, the largest range of non-outlier values
 410 was in Greece and Italy_MIC. The Total Risk values for other physical disturbance were in cases similar or
 411 usually lower than those for abrasion and sealing (Figure 6).

412 Figure 6: Distribution of Total Risk (%) by pressure for all MS in a logarithmic scale.

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 414 Concerning BHT, the Total Risk values for all 5 pressures were generally higher in soft BHT (Figure 7).

415 Figure 7: Distribution of Total Risk (%) by BHT for all MS.

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417 In Greece the most impacted habitat was Upper bathyal Soft followed by other soft habitats. In Croatia,
418 the soft habitats presented higher risk as well, however, Upper bathyal Hard habitat also presented a
419 significant Total Risk value. In Slovenia, the most impacted BHT was Circalittoral Soft. In Italy_MAD Upper
420 bathyal habitats and Circalittoral Soft presented most outliers and the largest ranges, whereas in
421 Italy_MIC and Italy_MWE Total Risk values for Bathyal habitats were one, two or three orders of
422 magnitude higher than the median Total Risk values for other BHTs (Figure 7).

424 4. Discussion

425 The risk assessment approach proposed, linking human activities in the marine environment to generated
426 pressures that impact the seafloor and its components, constitutes an ecosystem-wide assessment
427 methodology of the seafloor environmental status that can be used at both national and subregional/
428 regional level and applied to every marine region/subregion for Ecosystem-based management purposes.
429 The activities-pressures matrix can act as an easily applicable screening tool of human activities taking
430 place in the assessment area, associated to generated pressures. This association of activities and
431 pressures is further related to ecosystem components. Through the assessment of the specified activities-
432 pressures-habitat types linkage chains, based on quantitative data as well as qualitative expert judgement,
433 the linkage chains posing the greatest risk were identified. Having knowledge of interactions of high risk,
434 the necessary measures can be prioritized and consequently structure the framework towards the
435 reduction of physical impact on the seafloor and Ecosystem-based management.

436 Similar risk screening and assessment methodologies have been used in the Mediterranean and
437 elsewhere. These include for example Micheli et al. 2013 working in the Mediterranean and the Black Sea,
438 Knights et al. 2015 working on 4 regional seas, and ICES (2019b) in multiple European subregions. Piante
439 and Ody (2015) have focused on the Mediterranean and assessed current risks to Good Environmental
440 Status (*sensu* MSFD) due to existing and expanding Blue Growth human activities in the region. They
441 supplemented their analysis with regional and national chapters with detailed spatial layers where
442 available (e.g. oil-rigs, seismic activity, maritime traffic). At the time they concluded that there is a high
443 risk of failing to achieve GES in the Mediterranean Sea by 2020 for 7 out of 11 of the descriptors of the
444 MSFD. More recently, other more spatially explicit approaches have also been used to assess the
445 combined effects of human pressures on European marine ecosystems (Korpinen et al., 2021).

446 Our results suggest that abrasion represents the most intense pressure in Italy (considering all assessment
447 areas) and Greece, whereas sealing was the most intense pressure in Croatia. In Slovenia, sealing slightly
448 outweighed abrasion, however, abrasion due to small scale fish and shellfish harvesting was the top
449 pressure in Slovenia (small coastline and predominant small-scale fleet). All MS attributed abrasion to
450 demersal fishing and small scale harvesting as well as Tourism and leisure activities and it was shown that
451 it poses the greatest threat to the marine environment impacting most of the habitats. Abrasion in (very)
452 shallow waters is attributed to ship anchoring and even passage of ships and propeller induced turbulence
453 (e.g. in harbours) (Argüello, et al., 2022; Watson, et al., 2022) as well as coastal recreational anchoring
454 (e.g. in *Posidonia oceanica* beds) (Carreño, et al., 2019). Abrasion can be finely mapped in shallow waters
455 with new technologies (e.g. drones, aerial photos) (Bonacorsi, et al., 2013; Deter et al., 2017) based on
456 the footprint (Pergent-Martini, et al., 2022) of the activities on the seabed, and its spatial extent, intensity,
457 persistence and impacts assessed (e.g. on benthic communities and ecosystem service supply). Sealing, a
458 pressure of recognised regional importance (Knights, et al., 2015; EEA, 2006) was attributed by all or most
459 MS to Transport infrastructure, Coastal defence & flood protection, Tourism and leisure infrastructure,
460 with the dominant cause being the placement of permanent structures. Other physical disturbance and
461 other physical loss, attributed to Fish and shellfish harvesting (professional, recreational) demersal, were
462 among the top 5 pressures in Croatia and Slovenia.

463 The outcomes of the present methodology provide a satisfactory risk assessment of the exhaustive list of
464 activities generating physical pressures exerted on the seafloor of Croatia, Greece, Italy, and Slovenia, as

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well as at the Adriatic Sea subregion. As a semi-qualitative approach, it is of greater use in areas of limited data availability, or of spatial imbalance in data availability, such as the Mediterranean marine region (Gorjanc, et al., 2021; Paramana et al., 2021). Expert judgement (e.g., based on assumed overlap or frequency or extent of pressures/activities) is incorporated in the process to fill in the gap of accurate spatial data (such as data provided by VMS and IAS), constituting a challenge in itself. Adjustments, compared to Knights, et al. (2015) were needed and developed here to address the challenges (e.g., moving away from expressing trawling as months per year while also revisiting the scores for frequency). The estimated results that identified key pressures and those ecological components more at risk can support prioritizing measures by activity, or ecological component. This study also highlighted the need for consistency in terminology and its application in assessments as a means to allow true comparability of the results between and within sub-regions.

Although such an approach can lack precision to some extent compared to a fully quantitative methodology, if applied under a set of guidelines that can safeguard a common approach and rationale, as was realized in the present case, consistency can be achieved, and a reliable risk assessment of the marine environment can be performed. Hence, the approach is a structured assessment of the risks to seafloor integrity to be implemented in Ecosystem-based management (EBM) on a scale relevant to current environmental policy. For the process, to be reproducible and transparent, a clear definition on how spatial footprint is assessed and weights are applied is necessary, presently achieved through the methodology consolidation. Given that management resources are restricted and, thus, inadequate to deal with all issues, this framework can act as a decision-support tool so that managers can scientifically support management decisions in an Ecosystem-based management context, identifying key pressures and, thus, guiding the setting of priorities for measures.

The steps of the present methodology can be applied to other MSFD descriptors as well to provide evidence of the intensity and distribution of pressures and combined effects, providing that activities and pressures are selected accordingly, or conduct a full assessment of the marine area of interest integrating all MSFD activities, pressures, and ecosystem components allowing screening for risks and prioritizing linkage chains for management (ICES, 2021a). Integration of assessments from national to (sub)regional level (as in the case of the Adriatic Sea in the present study) entails the need of weighting impact and risk scores considering spatial ration of national waters over the region, to prevent distortions. This allows to provide a (sub)regional approach to the relative role of different pressures in an integrated manner.

Currently the approach does not incorporate any MSFD thresholds towards GES or have any obvious alignment with such thresholds. However, it could be possible to revisit certain aspects of it, e.g., the Spatial Extent boundaries to match those of the D6 Physical loss and Disturbance thresholds. The Marine Strategy Framework Directive (EC, 2017b) explicitly requires the establishment of thresholds for both loss and disturbance. For loss, MSFD criterion D6C4 (EC, 2017b) requires that the extent of loss of the habitat type, resulting from anthropogenic pressures, does not exceed a specified proportion of the natural extent of the habitat type in the assessment area. It also specifies that MS shall establish the maximum allowable extent of habitat loss as a proportion of the total natural extent of the habitat type, through cooperation at Union level, considering regional or subregional specificities. Similar requirements and a Union led process are specified for disturbance with MSFD criterion D6C5 (EC, 2017b).

Discussions between TG Seabed (mandated to provide guidance, recommendations, and proposals for adoption by the MS to the Commission) and Commission Expert Group on Strategic Coordination for the MSFD (MSCG) led to threshold values be decided upon and set at 25% for disturbance, including a 2% for loss (EC and TGSeabed, 2023). Therefore, for a seabed habitat to be considered in GES, no more than 25% of its extent should be adversely affected by human pressures, while no more than 2% should be irreversibly lost. A further threshold of a proportion of areas free from physical pressures (e.g., 5-15% of each habitat type) is also being discussed, as well as a quality threshold linked to acceptable deviation from GES is expected in 2024 (personal communication with TG Seabed members). Considering the above,

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4 513 further alignments of the assessment criteria used in this methodology will increase its applicability to
5 514 MSFD. For example, having a 5- or 7-level scale for spatial extent overlap, instead of current 3 (Table 2),
6 515 would be very useful in order to incorporate the above spatial extent thresholds, offering finer resolution
7 516 groupings. Likewise, although this is an assessment of risk and not of impacts per se, a better alignment
8 517 of the Degree of Impact (3-point scale currently) in terms of loss and occurrence of adverse effects would
9 518 be beneficial for policy implementation.
10 519

11 520 **5. Conclusions**

12 521 Achieving a proper management of the marine environment requires accurate and thorough assessments
13 522 of its environmental status. To this end, assessments conducted by the use of quantitative data covering
14 523 a period of time over which recovery is deemed possible (ICES, 2019), are regarded as best practice, as
15 524 they can depict the environmental status in greater detail. Nevertheless, in the cases where data
16 525 availability is scarce or fragmented, or data is completely lacking, qualitative/semi-qualitative assessments
17 526 as the one suggested herein, which allow the integration of expert judgement, are considered to be best
18 527 practice. Where spatially explicit data is insufficient or geographically unbalanced, and the assessment of
19 528 seabed habitats is mostly qualitative, for example in the Mediterranean Sea region (EC, 2020), the
20 529 suggested methodological approach can be a valuable tool supporting screening and decision making
21 530 processes. By incorporating available data and information and applying expert judgement, this approach
22 531 enables the assessment of pressures exerted on the marine environment assisting decision makers in
23 532 prioritizing management actions such as targeted measures and monitoring, required for the sustainable
24 533 use of the marine environment.

25 534 The 6-year implementation cycle of the MSFD allows adequate time to record improvements of the
26 535 seafloor status in its assessments, since it has been proved that the recovery of most benthic communities
27 536 is likely to occur within this timeframe, even in cases where the seafloor is severely impacted by physical
28 537 disturbance by towed gears (Hiddink, et al., 2017). Taking into account that some benthic habitats and
29 538 species might take longer to recover (e.g. coral reefs or seagrass meadows) the MSFD definition of a
30 539 permanent change equivalent to loss is set to 12 years (i.e., two MSFD assessment cycles) (EC, 2022).
31 540 Having therefore, a longer period to evaluate pressures can lead to a more reliable impact assessment of
32 541 activities generating these pressures (ICES, 2019a) while, also, allowing time for management measures
33 542 to reveal their effectiveness (Gorjanc et al., 2021).

34 543 Aligned with the MSFD 6-year assessment cycle the proposed approach can support the implementation
35 544 of Descriptor 6, while contributing to the requirements of the Barcelona Convention Integrated
36 545 Monitoring and Assessment Programme of the Mediterranean Sea and Coast (IMAP) Ecological Objective
37 546 6 to maintain seafloor integrity especially in priority benthic habitats. Future applications of the method
38 547 could include the 'recovery lag' criteria of the Knights et al. (2015) method. Nevertheless, this would
39 548 require reviewing and better aligning the scales for 'persistence' of the pressures in years after the
40 549 cessation of the activity and 'resilience/recovery' of ecological characteristics in years to pre-impact
41 550 conditions. Both variables are currently defined in a 4-point scale ranging from less than 2 years to over
42 551 100 years.

43 552 Therefore, the suggested approach can be a valuable tool for policymakers and managers in implementing
44 553 ecosystem-based management and advancing towards the reduction of physical impacts on the seafloor
45 554 caused by pressures. Having a rich toolkit with methods incorporating elements of risk to ecosystem
46 555 components, cumulative impacts and spatial extent of activities and pressures supports both taking EBM
47 556 decisions to reverse the situation if areas are failing to achieve GES under the MSFD (Borja et al., 2023)
48 557 and the implementation of the Maritime Spatial Planning Directive (MSPD) by achieving the needed but
49 558 still missing coherence between these two major policy instruments (Paramana et al., 2023).
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